

Fig1-2 file name	Description
Fig1_TKE_rz_v45_sfc6_LU.nc Fig1_wind_rz_sfc6_LU.nc	Data for TKE and wind x-z plots for 3 LES experiments (Figs. 1 and S2)
Fig1_wind_rz_sfc6_LU.nc	Data for Figs. 2 and S3

Fig3-4_data.zip	Item list
Fig3_cm1out_s_121.nc	CM1 output at t = 2h (Fig. 3)
x-1km_lu18_101sonde_midP-flagU3-dt1s.nc x-3km_lu18_101sonde_midP-flagU3-dt1s.nc x-6km_lu18_101sonde_midP-flagU3-dt1s.nc	Wind profiles of 101 sondes released at x = –1, –3, –6 km (Figs. 3 and 4a–c)
Fig4_sonde_v10_z0.nc	Data for Figs. 4d-i